

Valorization of Agricultural Waste and CO₂ into Bioderived Cyclic Carbonates

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Graphical Abstract

Waste-derived oils have been epoxidized and used with CO₂ as starting materials for the synthesis of cyclic carbonates

Highlights

- Valorization of agricultural waste-derived oils for the synthesis of high value-added chemicals with potential applications as building blocks.
- Highly active, effective, and recyclable metal-free catalysts for the carboxylation of epoxides with CO₂ under solvent-free conditions.
- Synthesis of eleven waste oil-derived cyclic carbonates from their corresponding epoxides and CO₂ without the need of a co-catalyst in 85–97% isolated yield.

Abstract

Eleven bio-derived epoxides **2a–k** have been synthesized from their corresponding waste vegetable oils (**1a–k**). These epoxides are potential starting materials themselves for the preparation of a broad range of chemical products and bio-derived polymers such as polyether or polyester materials. In this contribution, epoxides **2a–k** and carbon dioxide have been used as renewable feedstocks for the synthesis of cyclic carbonates **5a–k** in excellent isolated yields (85–97%) using the highly efficient and metal-free bifunctional imidazole-based organocatalyst **4b** under solvent-free conditions. The preparation of cyclic carbonates **5a–g**, in which oleic acid is the major component, has been performed at 100 °C and 20 bar CO₂ pressure for 16 hours using 1 mol% of catalyst **4b**. In addition, cyclic carbonates **5h–k** have been synthesized under the same reaction conditions (80 °C, 20 bar CO₂ pressure for 16 hours) using different catalyst loading of **4b** (2 mol% for **5h–j** and 3 mol% for **5k**). Finally, a reusability study of organocatalyst **4b** was performed under the optimized reaction conditions keeping constant the catalytic activity and stability of **4b** for at least 5 days.

Keywords: CO₂ utilization; Renewable agricultural waste; Cyclic carbonates; Organocatalyst; Sustainable catalysis

1. Introduction

Society demands the development of new products and chemical processes that make our planet more sustainable. Thus, the design of novel chemical products is currently very related to the sustainability of the process and is highly desirable to reduce or eliminate hazards within the chemicals and processes in order to meet the “Twelve Principles of Green Chemistry” [1]. In the last few years, waste production has increased enormously, which has a huge negative impact on the environment. Subsequently, the scientific

community is currently focused on developing novel strategies to reduce waste generation and increase waste valorization. Agri-residues have attracted much attention in the last decade due to their high volumes [2–6]. For the design of new sustainable catalytic processes, unavoidable agricultural waste must be used as starting material instead of food-derived feedstocks and must be carried out under relatively mild reaction conditions (Fig. 1) [2–6].

Among the produced agri-residues, vegetable oils and/or their residual cakes, which are produced from a variety of oleaginous fruits, seeds and nut crops are cheaper than refined vegetable oils, can be a potential renewable feedstock for the preparation of high value-added chemicals such as olefins [7,8] and bio-diesel [9–14].

Fig. 1. Potential compounds derived from agricultural waste.

On the other hand, the increase of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions in the atmosphere is one the main causes of global warming [15]. Therefore, the development of novel synthetic strategies using CO₂ as starting material for the synthesis of high value-added

chemical products [16–20] is required in order to avoid CO₂ emissions instead of reducing the amount of CO₂ in the atmosphere [21–23]. Therefore, much research has been devoted to the use of carbon dioxide (CO₂) as renewable C₁ building block for the synthesis of chemical products [24–28] since CO₂ is easily available, non-toxic, non-flammable and an inexpensive source [29,30]. One of the most studied processes is the reaction of CO₂ with epoxides to afford cyclic carbonates (Scheme 1) [31–44]. These organic products have found important applications, such as electrolytes in lithium-ion batteries [45–47], sustainable solvents [48–50] and chemical intermediates [51,52]. Although the preparation of cyclic carbonates has been a commercial process for a long time, current commercial processes require high temperature and carbon dioxide pressure [53,54]. Therefore, many catalyst systems have been recently developed to prepare cyclic carbonates at lower temperatures and CO₂ pressures in order to make this process more energy efficient [29,30,55–64].

Scheme 1. Reaction of CO₂ and epoxides for the synthesis of cyclic carbonates.

Bio-based epoxides derived from waste vegetable oils can be synthesized by epoxidation of the olefinic groups of the triglyceride units [65,66]. These epoxides have received much attention since they could be used as starting materials for the preparation of bio-based polyesters by reaction with anhydrides through a Ring-Opening Copolymerization (ROCOP) process (Scheme 2a) [66]. Moreover, these epoxides can be used for the synthesis of bio-derived cyclic carbonates by reaction with CO₂ (Scheme 2b)

[59,67–69]. It is worth noting that bio-derived cyclic carbonates have acquired great importance as building blocks for the preparation of non-isocyanate polyurethanes (NIPUs) by reaction with diamines (Scheme 2c) [70–79].

Scheme 2. Synthetic route for the preparation of bio-derived polyesters (a), cyclic carbonates (b) or NIPUs (c).

However, the preparation of these cyclic carbonates is generally carried out at high temperatures and CO_2 pressures [74,75,80–82]. Our research group has reported several catalytic systems which have shown to be highly active and selective for cyclic carbonates formation [57,58,83–90]. As far as we know, there are few catalysts able to perform the preparation of some of these waste vegetable oils-derived cyclic carbonates [60,67,71,75]. Herein we report the use of bifunctional organocatalysts for the synthesis of eleven waste oil-derived cyclic carbonates from their corresponding epoxides and CO_2

under relatively mild reaction conditions in order to reduce agricultural residues and their subsequently valorization into useful chemical products that could be potentially employed as substrates for the preparation of NIPUs. It is worth highlighting that some of the agricultural wastes used in this work have not been previously used for the preparation of renewable cyclic carbonates. Only a few catalysts are able to perform the preparation of some of these waste vegetable oils-derived cyclic carbonates.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials and methods

All manipulations involving CO₂ were performed in a stainless-steel reactor with a magnetic stirrer bar. Solvents were pre-dried over sodium wire (*n*-hexane, Et₂O, EtOAc) or CaCl₂ (CH₂Cl₂). Deuterated solvents were stored over activated 4 Å molecular sieves and degassed by several freeze-thaw cycles. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian Inova FT-500 spectrometer and referenced to the residual deuterated solvent. DEPT-135 spectra were recorded with the following acquisition parameters: irradiation time 2 s and number of scans 256, using standard VARIAN-FT software. FTIR spectra were obtained on a Shimadzu IR Prestige-21 spectrophotometer equipped with a Pike Technology ATR system. The instrument was set to acquire 32 scans per spectrum at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. Commercially available chemicals (Alfa, Aldrich, Fluka) were used as received. Fatty acid compositions of all vegetable oils were determined according to previous reported procedures [91].

2.2 Oil extraction

Oils **1a–k** were extracted using a screw press (Komet Screw Vegetable Oil Expeller CA59G-CA563, IBG Monforts Oekotec GmbH & Co. KG, Mönchengladbach, Germany) equipped with a 3 mm diameter Nozzle, operating at a screw speed of 30 rpm, from the

residual cake (secondary product from the elaboration process of virgin seed/nut oils) at a pressing temperature of 80 °C. The screw press was first run empty for 10–15 min to raise the screw-press barrel temperature for the extraction, using the electrical resistance ring attached around the press barrel. The resulting oil was centrifuged at 5000 rpm to remove the residual plant material. Oil samples were stored in amber bottles, without headspace, to protect them from light. All samples were stored in the dark at 4 °C until analyzed.

2.3 Fatty acid composition

The methyl esters were prepared by vigorous shaking of a solution of oil in heptane (0.5 g in 3 mL) with 0.5 mL of 2 N methanolic potassium hydroxide and then analyzed by GC using an Agilent Technologies (HP 6890; Santa Clara, CA) chromatograph equipped with a FID detector. A fused silica capillary column (60 m length × 0.25 mm i.d.) coated with SPTTM-2380 phase (0.2 µm thickness, Supelco, Madrid, Spain) was used. Helium was used as the carrier gas at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. The injector and detector temperature were set at 220 and 250 °C, respectively. The oven temperature was maintained at 185 °C and the injection volume was 1 µL in split injection mode. Individual fatty acid were expressed as a percentage of the total, according to the European Regulation (EC)2568/91 and subsequent amendments, corresponding to the American Oil Chemists' Society (AOCS) method Ch 2–91 [92].

2.4 Synthesis of Epoxidized Vegetable Oils

Epoxidized vegetable oils were prepared following a synthetic route previously reported method.[65] Vegetable oils and formic acid (1:4 molar ratio) were placed into a 100 mL round bottom flask at 60 °C under powerful stirring. Then, H₂O₂ 30 % w/w (2:1 molar ratio of H₂O₂ per double bond in triglyceride unit) was slowly added over a period of 3 h

(the addition of H₂O₂ should be done carefully and slowly to avoid any safety problem) (Scheme S1 in Supplementary data) and the reaction was stirred at 60 °C for another 3 h. Then, diethyl ether was added (100 mL) and the resulting solution was washed with a saturated aqueous solution of NaHCO₃ (2 x 100 mL). The organic layer was dried with MgSO₄ overnight, filtered and concentrated (rotary evaporation) to give the epoxidized vegetable oil as a white solid (**2a–g**) or as a colorless oil (**2h–k**). The product was further purified by column chromatography through a plug of silica gel using a solvent system *n*-hexane/EtOAc (1:1).

2.5 General procedure for the synthesis of bioderived cyclic carbonates 5a–k

An epoxidized vegetable oil **2a–k** (5.0 mmol) and organocatalyst **3a–b** or **4a–b** (0.05–0.15 mmol) were placed in a 50 mL stainless-steel reactor with a magnetic stirrer bar and a thermocouple to regulate the temperature of the reaction mixture (See Supporting Information). Then, the reactor was sealed and pressurized at 20 bar with CO₂ and the reaction mixture was stirred at 80–100 °C for 16 h. After that, the reactor was cooled and depressurized. Once the reactor was open, the conversion of epoxide **2a–k** to cyclic carbonate **5a–k** was then determined by analysis of a sample by ¹H NMR spectroscopy. Conversions were determined by comparison of the integrals of resonances from the methine (CH) protons for cyclic carbonates and epoxides in the ¹H NMR spectra. Then, the mixture was purified by flash chromatography through a plug of silica gel using a solvent system of first hexane, then hexane/EtOAc (9:1), then hexane/ EtOAc (3:1), then EtOAc to give the pure cyclic carbonates **5a–k**.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Epoxidation of waste vegetable oils

Waste vegetable oils from different sources, such as oleaginous seeds (sunflower, rapeseed, pumpkin, flaxseed and grapeseed), nuts (hazelnut, pistachio, almond and walnut) and fruits (olive/pomace), were used as renewable feedstock for the preparation of their corresponding epoxidized vegetable oils. Their fatty acids composition was determined by GC-FID (See Experimental Section, Table 1 and Supplementary data). These oils were classified based on their composition considering the number of double bonds per triglyceride unit (oxirane number) in three different groups, oleic acid (18:1), linoleic acid (18:2) and linolenic acid (18:3). As can be seen in Table 1, oleic acid was the major fatty acid in vegetable oils **1a–g**, linoleic acid was the predominant fatty acid in oils **1h–j** and linolenic acid was the major component in linseed oil **1k**.

Once the composition of the waste vegetable oils **1a–k** was determined, those were epoxidized under standard conditions (See Scheme 3, Experimental Section and Supplementary data for further details).[65] It is worth highlighting that epoxides in which oleic acid was the mayor component **2a–g**, were isolated as white solids whereas epoxides **2h–j** and **2k** in which linoleic and linolenic acids were the major component respectively, were isolated as colorless oils.

Table 1. Fatty acid composition of waste vegetable oils.^a

Oil	(16:0) ^b (%)	(16:1) ^c (%)	(18:0) ^d (%)	(18:1) (%)	(18:2) (%)	(18:3) (%)	Ox. Num. (mmol/g) ^e	Classif.
High Oleic								
Sunflower (1a)	4.4	0.2	2.7	90.4	1.5	0.4	2.84	Oleic
Hazelnut (1b)	6.1	0.2	2.6	79.9	10.3	0.3	3.07	Oleic
Olive (1c)	14.2	1.5	3.9	70.4	8.0	1.0	2.73	Oleic

Pistachio (1d)	9.4	0.9	2.1	73.6	12.8	0.6	3.06	Oleic
Almond (1e)	6.4	0.6	2.1	73.4	17.1	0.1	3.25	Oleic
Rapeseed (1f)	4.4	0.2	1.7	65.1	17.1	10.7	3.99	Oleic
Pumpkin seed (1g)	16.0	0.1	8.3	28.2	46.7	-	3.65	Oleic
Walnut (1h)	7.3	0.1	2.6	15.1	62.4	12.5	5.32	Linoleic
Sunflower (1i)	5.8	0.1	5.9	33.4	53.8	0.2	4.25	Linoleic
Grape seed (1j)	6.9	0.1	4.0	19.0	69.1	0.3	4.75	Linoleic
Flaxseed (1k)	5.0	0.1	3.8	17.9	16.8	55.9	6.58	Linolenic

^aDetermined by GC-FID. ^bPalmitic acid. ^cPalmitoleic acid. ^dStearic acid. ^eOx. Number: Number of double bonds per gram of triglyceride unit. Ox. Number = $(\sum \% \text{fatty acid} \cdot x)/100$; x = total number of double bonds per triglyceride unit.

Scheme 3. Epoxidation of vegetable oil into their corresponding epoxides.

3.2. Synthesis of bifunctional catalysts

Organocatalysts **3a–b** and **4a–b** were prepared following a modified synthetic route of our previously reported method.[86] Bifunctional catalysts were obtained in high yield by a base-induced 1,3-cycloaddition reaction of tosylmethylisocyanide (TosMIC) and imines to form the neutral imidazole derivatives, followed by reaction with 1-bromobutane or 1-iodobutane at 100 °C (Scheme 4). These bifunctional metal-free

organocatalysts have a number of advantages, such as the use of inexpensive and commercially available precursors in a two-step procedure, avoid issues with sustainability of metal supply and removal of traces of metals from the product, easy separation of catalyst, and possibility of large-scale industrial applications. Moreover, these catalysts lack of sensitivity to moisture and air, therefore, there is no need to use a glovebox or an inert atmosphere when studying the reaction between epoxides and CO₂.

Scheme 4. Synthesis of bifunctional organocatalysts.

3.3. Catalytic formation of cyclic carbonates by reaction of epoxidized oils and CO₂

Given the different composition of the synthesized epoxides (oleic, linoleic, or linolenic as major fatty acids) we decided to optimize the reaction condition for each one of the different epoxidized triglycerides using compounds **3a–b** and **4a–b** as catalysts (Scheme 5). Firstly, we studied the preparation of cyclic carbonates which contain oleic acid as major component **5a–g** by reaction of their corresponding epoxides **2a–g** and CO₂. To optimize the reaction conditions, epoxidized high oleic sunflower oil **2a** was chosen as a representative substrate (Scheme 5 and Table 2). Reactions were carried out in a 30 mL steel reactor at 80–100 °C and 20 bar CO₂ pressure for 16 h using bifunctional catalysts **3a–b** and **4a–b** under solvent-free conditions. Polycarbonate formation was not observed under the aforementioned reaction conditions.

Scheme 5. Synthesis of high oleic sunflower carbonate **5a**.

It should be noted that the catalytic reaction is very sensitive to the reaction temperature (Table 2). When the reactions were carried out at 80 °C, very low conversions were achieved for the synthesis of carbonated high oleic sunflower oil **5a**, due to the solid nature of epoxide **2a** (Table 2, entries 1–4). Therefore, the reaction temperature was increased up to 100 °C at which epoxide **2a** was a colorless oil and compounds **3a–b** and **4a–b** were soluble in it. Under these reaction conditions, compounds **4a–b** displayed higher catalytic activity than catalysts **3a–b** showing that the substituent on the nitrogen atom of the imine plays an important role on the catalytic activity (N–Bu > N–Ph). This is probably due to a higher solubility of the bifunctional catalysts in the epoxidized oil.

Table 2. Conversion of **2a** into **5a** using catalysts **3a–b** and **4a–b**.^a

Entry	Cat. (mol%)	Temperature (°C)	Conversion (%) ^b
1	3a (3.0 mol%)	80	Traces
2	3b (3.0 mol%)	80	Traces
3	4a (3.0 mol%)	80	5
4	4b (3.0 mol%)	80	3
5	3a (3.0 mol%)	100	58

6	3b (3.0 mol%)	100	73
7	4a (3.0 mol%)	100	100
8	4b (3.0 mol%)	100	100
9	4a (2.0 mol%)	100	100
10	4b (2.0 mol%)	100	100
11	4a (1.0 mol%)	100	75
12	4b (1.0 mol%)	100	97

^aReactions were carried out at 80–100 °C and 20 bar CO₂ pressure for 16 hours.

^bDetermined by ¹H NMR spectroscopy.

As can be seen in Table 2, entries 7 and 8, quantitative conversion was obtained using 3 mol% of both organocatalysts **4a–b**. Then, the effect of the catalyst loading on the catalytic activity was studied (Table 2, entries 5–12). Excellent conversion was achieved when the catalyst loading was reduced to 1 mol% using organocatalyst **4b**, which contains an iodide counterion (Table 2, entry 12), at 100 °C and 20 bar CO₂ pressure. The higher catalytic activity of catalyst **4b** may be due to the greater nucleophilicity and leaving group ability of the iodide anion compared to bromide anion. Moreover, the electrostatic interaction between the iodide anion and the ammonium cation is weaker than that for the bromide anion due to the ion pairing effect. Thus, the iodide is further away from the ammonium cation and subsequently, the nucleophilic attack of the halide on the epoxide is favored [93–96].

Cyclic carbonate **5a** was characterized by spectroscopic methods (see the Experimental Section). ¹H NMR spectra of cyclic carbonate **5a**, epoxide **2a** and high oleic sunflower oil precursor **1a** are shown in Fig. 2. It is worth noting that the signals corresponding to the CH protons in the α -position of cyclic carbonate **5a** are shifted to low field (4.20–4.60

ppm, Fig. 2c) with respect to the resonance of the CH protons in the α -position of the epoxy function of compound **2a** (2.81–3.13ppm, Fig. 2b). IR spectroscopy is an efficient tool to study the formation of C=O carbonyl functional groups. Thus, two new characteristic bands were observed at 1799 and 1045 cm^{-1} in the FTIR spectrum which correspond to the C=O carbonyl and C–O stretching frequencies in cyclic carbonates respectively that confirmed the formation of carbonated high oleic sunflower oil **5a** (See Experimental Section and Supplementary data for further details).

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR spectra of: (a) high oleic sunflower oil **1a**; (b) epoxidized high oleic sunflower oil **2a**; (c) carbonated high oleic sunflower oil **5a** in CDCl₃.

Given the catalytic potential of bifunctional organocatalyst **4b** for the synthesis of high oleic sunflower carbonate **5a**, we explored its use as catalyst for the preparation of waste oil-derived cyclic carbonates (**5a–g**) in which the major fatty acid is oleic acid. We were pleased to find that compound **4b** was able to efficiently promote the synthesis of cyclic

carbonates **5a–g** with excellent conversions and isolated yields from their corresponding epoxides **2a–g** and CO₂ (Table 3, entries 1–7). It is worth highlighting that the use of waste vegetable oils **1b**, **1d–g** as starting materials for the synthesis of cyclic carbonates with potential applications as bio-derived building blocks, has not been previously reported.

Table 3. Conversion of **2a–2g** into **5a–5g** using catalysts **4b**.^a

Entry	Oil-derived epoxides	Conversion (%) ^b	Yield (%) ^c
1	High oleic sunflower (2a)	97	95
2	Hazelnut (2b)	98	91
3	Olive (2c)	98	96
4	Pistachio (2d)	99	93
5	Almond (2e)	98	95
6	Rapeseed (2f)	99	94
7	Pumpkin seed (2g)	97	92

^aReactions were carried out at 100 °C and 20 bar CO₂ pressure for 16 hours using 1 mol% of compound **4b**. ^bDetermined by ¹H NMR spectroscopy. ^cIsolated yield.

Inspired by the high catalytic activity displayed by catalyst **4b** for the synthesis of cyclic carbonates **5a–g**, then we focused our efforts on the preparation of cyclic carbonates **5h–j** from their corresponding epoxides **2h–j** in which the major fatty acid is linoleic acid (Scheme 6). The reaction conditions for the synthesis of **5h–j** were optimized using epoxide **2h** as model substrate. Since epoxides **2h–j** were colorless oils, catalysts **3a–b** and **4a–b** were soluble in them so the reactions could be carried out at 80 °C and 20 bar CO₂ pressure for 16 h under solvent-free conditions. Then the effect of the catalyst loading on the catalytic activity of **3a–b** and **4a–b** was investigated (Table 4).

Scheme 6. Synthesis of cyclic carbonates **5h-j**.

Table 4 collects the data for the optimization of the reaction conditions for the synthesis of cyclic carbonates **5h-j**. Similar to what was previously observed, compounds **4a-b** showed higher catalytic activity than catalysts **3a-b** (N-Bu > N-Ph) (Table 4, entries 1-4). Since quantitative conversion of epoxide **2h** into cyclic carbonate **5h** was achieved using catalysts **4a-b** using 3.0 mol% of catalyst loading, the effect of reducing the amount of catalyst was investigated (Table 4, entries 3-10). Complete conversion was obtained when using 2.5 mol% of catalyst loading of either organocatalyst **4a** or **4b** (Table 4, entries 5-6). Decreasing the catalyst loading down to 1.5 mol% resulted in a reduction of their catalytic activity and lower conversions were observed, 49% and 72% for catalyst **4a** and **4b** respectively (Table 4, entries 9-10). In the same way to what was found for the synthesis of cyclic carbonates **5a-g**, iodide derivative **4b** displayed higher catalytic activity than the bromide containing organocatalyst **4a** (Table 4, entries 7-8). Therefore, we selected 2.0 mol% of compound **4b** as optimal catalyst at 80 °C and 20 bar CO₂ pressure for 16 h since almost quantitative conversion was achieved. Finally, the preparation of carbonated sunflower oil **5i** and carbonated grape seed oil **5j** was carried out under the optimal reaction conditions, obtaining 92% and 85% isolated yield

respectively (Table 4, entries 11–12). It is relevant to note that the use of walnut oil **1h** as precursor for the synthesis of cyclic carbonate **5h** has been reported for the first time in this work.

Table 4. Conversion of epoxides **2h–j** into cyclic carbonates **5h–j** using catalysts **3a–b** and **4a–b**^a

Entry	Epoxide	Cat. (mol%)	Conversion (%) ^b
1	Walnut (2h)	3a (3.0 mol%)	69
2	Walnut (2h)	3b (3.0 mol%)	79
3	Walnut (2h)	4a (3.0 mol%)	100
4	Walnut (2h)	4b (3.0 mol%)	100
5	Walnut (2h)	3 (2.5 mol%)	100
6	Walnut (2h)	4 (2.5 mol%)	100
7	Walnut (2h)	3 (2.0 mol%)	70
8 ^c	Walnut (2h)	4 (2.0 mol%)	97 (95)
9	Walnut (2h)	3 (1.5 mol%)	49
10	Walnut (2h)	4 (1.5 mol%)	72
11 ^c	Sunflower (2i)	3 (2.0 mol%)	96 (92)
12 ^c	Grape Seed (2j)	4 (2.0 mol%)	90 (85)

^aReactions were carried out at 80 °C and 20 bar CO₂ pressure for 16 h. ^bDetermined by ¹H NMR spectroscopy. ^cIsolated yield in parenthesis.

The conversion of epoxides **2h–j** into cyclic carbonate **5h–j** was confirmed by ¹H and ¹³C{¹H} NMR and FTIR spectroscopy. Similar to what was previously observed, the ¹H NMR spectra of epoxides **2h–j** showed a set of signals around 2.85–3.25 ppm which were assigned to the CH protons of the epoxide moieties. The signals corresponding to the CH

groups of the cyclocarbonate moiety of compounds **5h–j** were shifted to lower field (4.25–5.00 ppm) with respect to the signals of the epoxide precursors (See Fig. 3), indicating the formation of the cyclic carbonate products (see Scheme 6). As an example, ¹H NMR spectra of waste walnut oil (**1h**), epoxidized walnut oil (**2h**) and carbonated walnut oil (**5h**) are shown in Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of cyclic carbonates **5h–j** exhibited a new band around 1800 cm⁻¹ which was assigned to the C=O carbonyl stretching that confirmed the formation of cyclic carbonates **5h–j** (see Experimental Section and Supplementary data).

Fig. 3. ¹H NMR spectra of waste walnut oil **1h** (a), epoxidized walnut oil **2h** (b) and carbonated walnut oil **5h** (c) in CDCl₃.

Finally, waste flaxseed oil **1k**, in which linolenic acid is the major fatty acid, was used for the synthesis of epoxidized flaxseed oil **2k** (Scheme 7). Since epoxide **2k** is an oil at room temperature, the reaction temperature for the synthesis of cyclic carbonate **5k** could be carried out at 80 °C (Scheme 7). As previously observed for the preparation of cyclic

carbonates **5a–j**, the iodide organocatalyst **4b** showed to be the most active catalyst at 80 °C using a range of catalyst loadings (Table 5). As can be seen in Table 5, the optimal catalyst loading for the synthesis of carbonated flaxseed oil **5k** was 3 mol% of compound **4b**, obtaining 99% conversion and 97% isolated yield of cyclic carbonate **5k** (Table 5, entry 12).

Scheme 7. Synthesis of cyclic carbonate **5k**.

Based on previous reports on organocatalyzed reactions [67,86,97–107] a plausible mechanism for the synthesis of cyclic carbonates derived from epoxidized waste vegetable oils and CO_2 is shown in Scheme 8. Firstly, the epoxide is activated via hydrogen bonding between the oxygen atom of the epoxide and the hydrogen atom of the $-\text{OH}$ group of compound **4b**, which facilitates the nucleophilic attack of the iodide to ring-open the epoxide and form an iodoalkoxide moiety. Then, CO_2 is inserted into the $\text{O}-\text{H}$ bond to generate a carbonate, which can then ring-close to produce the corresponding cyclic carbonate product and regenerate catalyst **4b**.

Table 5. Conversion of epoxidized flaxseed oil **2k** into carbonated flaxseed oil **5k** using catalysts **3a–b** and **4a–b**^a

Entry	Cat. (mol%)	Conversion (%) ^b
1	3a (2.0 mol%)	3
2	3b (2.0 mol%)	12
3	4a (2.0 mol%)	19
4	4b (2.0 mol%)	60
5	3a (2.5 mol%)	6
6	3b (2.5 mol%)	18
7	4a (2.5 mol%)	26
8	4b (2.5 mol%)	72
9	3a (3.0 mol%)	12
10	3b (3.0 mol%)	29
11	4a (3.0 mol%)	32
12 ^c	4b (3.0 mol%)	99 (97)

^aReactions were carried out at 80 °C and 20 bar CO₂ pressure for 16 h. ^bDetermined by ¹H NMR spectroscopy. ^cIsolated yield in parenthesis.

3.4. Reusability study of catalyst **4b**

Finally, a reusability study for organocatalyst **4b** was performed under the optimized reaction conditions using epoxidized high oleic sunflower oil **2a** as substrate following a previously reported procedure [108]. Catalyst **4b** and epoxide **2a** were placed in a stainless-steel reactor at 100 °C and the reactor was pressurized to 20 bar of carbon dioxide with a reaction time of 16 hours. Then the conversion of epoxide **2a** into cyclic carbonate **5a** was determined by NMR spectroscopy. The reusability study was performed

by addition of epoxide **2a** and fresh catalyst **4b** (1 mol%) to the reaction mixture after 16 hours in order to keep the concentration of catalyst constant to 1 mol%, and this procedure was repeated four times. As can be seen in Fig. 4, conversions of epoxide **2a** into cyclic carbonate **5a** of 97, 94, 93, 91 and 89% were obtained after 5 cycles. The results at 2 and 5 hours confirmed that catalyst **4b** is stable and can be reused since the catalytic activity is maintained. After the fifth cycle, Et₂O was added to the reaction mixture in order to precipitate catalyst **4b**. The reaction mixture was centrifuged and catalyst **4b** was recovered. The ¹H-NMR spectrum of the recovered catalyst **4b** showed no changes compared to freshly prepared compound **4b** (see Supplementary data).

Scheme 8. Plausible mechanism for the synthesis of waste vegetable oils-derived cyclic carbonates catalyzed by organocatalyst **4b**.

Fig. 4. Reusability study of catalyst **4b**.

The reusability of catalyst **4b** was further investigated on a multigram scale reaction under the optimal conditions by precipitation and isolation of **4b** after each cycle by adding diethyl ether. After isolation of compound **4b**, epoxide **2a** was added to run the following cycles. As can be seen in Table 6, no significant loss of catalytic activity was observed over five consecutive cycles. These results confirm that catalyst **4b** maintain the catalytic activity and stability under the optimized reaction conditions for at least 5 days.

Table 6. Reusability study of catalyst **4b**^a

Cycle	Catalyst (mmol) ^b	Catalyst Recovery (%) ^c	Conversion (%) ^d
1	0.25	95	100
2	0.2375	96	100
3	0.228	92	98
4	0.20976	94	98
5	0.1971744	91	96

^aReactions were carried out at 100 °C and 20 bar CO₂ pressure for 16 h using **2a** (25 mmol) and **4b** (0.25 mmol). ^bRecovered catalyst after previous cycle. ^cMass percentage of recovered catalyst after previous cycle. ^dDetermined by ¹H NMR spectroscopy.

As we have previously commented only a few catalysts are able to perform the preparation of some of these waste vegetables oils-derived cyclic carbonates. In general, quaternary ammonium salts have been used as catalysts to carry out this catalytic transformation although high reaction temperatures (≥ 110 °C) and CO₂ pressures (20–50 bar) were required [71,75,109,110]. Werner *et al.* have developed a set of organocatalysts [67] and a catalyst system based on the combination of CaI₂ and crown ether ligands [59], which have shown good catalytic activity for the preparation of this type of substrates under relatively mild reaction conditions (45–80 °C and 5–25 bar). The combination of ascorbic acid and tetrabutylammonium chloride accomplished the synthesis of **5c** at 100 °C and 5 bar of CO₂ pressure in 48 h in excellent yields [110].

4. Conclusions

In this work, we have developed a range of waste vegetables oils-derived epoxides and cyclic carbonates which could be used as potential bio-derived intermediates in different chemical processes. It is worth noting that some of the waste vegetables oils used in this work have not been previously used as starting materials for the synthesis of cyclic carbonates. Eleven bio-derived epoxides were synthesized from their corresponding waste vegetable oils from seeds, nuts and fruits. These epoxides are interesting substrates which can be used for the preparation of bio-derived cyclic carbonates by reaction with carbon dioxide using efficient bifunctional organocatalysts. Iodide derived organocatalyst showed to be the best catalyst system for the conversion of epoxides into their corresponding cyclic carbonates using a low catalyst load of 1.0–3.0 mol% under solvent free conditions. Further studies are being carried out to use these bio-oils derived epoxides and cyclic carbonates as scaffolds for the synthesis of bio-based adhesives and polymers such as polycarbonates or polyurethanes (NIPUs).

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Declaration of interests

Authors declare no competing financial interests.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data including experimental details, procedures for catalytic reactions, ^1H NMR for waste vegetable oils **1a–k**, ^1H NMR, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectra and FTIR for epoxides **2a–k** and ^1H NMR, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectra and IR for cyclic carbonates **5a–k**. Supplementary material related to this article can be found in the online version, at doi:XXXX

Abbreviations

ROCOP, Ring-Opening Copolymerization; NIPUs, non-isocyanate polyurethanes; GC-FID, Gas Chromatography with Flame-Ionization Detection; EC, European Regulation; AOCS, American Oil Chemists' Society; CO_2 , carbon dioxide.

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